

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE FUTURE OF LEARNING TECHNOLOGY WITH INNOVATIVE WAYS

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Abstract. *This article describes the process of developing innovative ways in Artificial Intelligence inventing of future robots in the case of a lack of manual or mental labor. Discussion about misconceptions on artificial intelligence and impact on transforming customer engagement. Seamless experiences. Research to ensure that artificial intelligence remains safe and beneficial. Benefits and risks of Artificial Intelligence.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, ability, risks and misconceptions, benefits, adoption, experience.*

Greg Clark MP, Chairman of the Science, Innovation and Technology Committee, said: *“Artificial Intelligence is already changing the way we live and its impact on our society and economy looks set to undergo explosive growth. AI is full of opportunity, but it also carries many dangerous risks to long-established and revered rights, from personal privacy to national security. People expect politicians to protect their rights”.*

INTRODUCTION

In the quest for sophistication, human beings have consistently developed and improved various technologies. The reason behind such practice is to ensure that they can come up with products that have the ability to provide an ease with how they carry out various methods. Various activities have been taking place since humans came into existence, as they sought to ensure to have a chance of serving in different environments found. The practice would culminate in the early 1760s during the industrial revolution. During the period, various countries saw it possible to create different products for the masses to meet the demand for different products as a result of growing populations. Human beings have gone notch higher since then, through the creation and adoption of artificial intelligence. The concept outlines the use of computer systems to perform tasks that usually need human intelligence. These are such as speech recognition, visual perception as well as decision-making. The paper aims to outline various benefits and risks and misconception associated with artificial intelligence about transforming customer engagement.

BENEFITS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificial intelligence has been found to have tremendous advantages. One of the benefits is that it has increased the level of performance of physicians at hospital facilities. The situation acts in the interest of patients who are regarded as customers. The hospital staff can use computer systems specially developed to identify patients who are most at risk. Such systems can precisely analyze the specific physiologic problems that various patients found at the hospital could be having and provide proper information about the patient who requires quick action. Through the process, the limited resources found at facilities could be used most efficiently to bring about the best outcomes, about ensuring they have the ability to meet the specific problems that patients may

be going through to generally improve their quality of life. Through such a process, computer systems are also able to aid in the process of decision-making and save physicians the time they would have needed to consult widely on some of the health problems that the patients could be experiencing. For instance, it has been used to determine the level of interaction of various drugs on patients to see if they have some antagonistic or synergistic effects on each other. Through the process of drug formulation, and clinical research, artificial intelligence has been used to analyze the vast amount of molecular information that relates to drug candidates to determine the general effects that it would have upon them. In such a way, it would have the opportunity of ensuring they have the ability to identify the general implications of the specific drugs they put in the market. Pharmaceutical companies can apparently look into the different characteristics of the drugs they are developing. The process would enable them to put up various measures that would help them deal with the side-effects that could be associated with the drugs they develop. Through the case, it ensures that such companies have the ability to provide the element of patient safety through the development of products that have a lesser chance of having adverse effects upon them.

Artificial intelligence also has a lot of importance in business. It is mostly used in the area of logistics by shipping companies to ensure they have the ability to move various cargo they are dealing with in the most appropriate fashion. Through the proper installation of a computer system, it can direct and monitor the movement of thousands of cargo in various parts of the world, to the point that they have the ability to reach the desired destination in time and make the particular company involved in such a case quite competitive. An example of such companies is the Port Botany container terminal found in Sydney, Australia. What the system puts in place can monitor various cargo that moves around to different destinations to ensure they have the ability to meet the needs of the different clients who could be in need of their products. The process aids in the proper movement of such products quite efficiently, given the fact that any problems that may be identified in the same could be dealt with in a way that would help ensure success. Through the use of artificial intelligence, logistics and shipping companies have the ability to identify any mishaps that could have happened in the supply chain for the purpose of increasing the chances of the best outcomes on some of the actions they would have put in place to achieve success. The finance and banking industry also make use of artificial intelligence to ensure they have the ability to monitor various activities that take place. Through the process, they can assess the different issues to make sure that suspicious acts such as fraud do not take place. Systems put in place are bound to look for the various malpractices that individuals could be involved in and obliged to bring in some problems about different forms of losses that companies could make at the end. Through the given case, there is a chance that they can help reduce the possibility of losses that the institutions could make. The process also contributes to strengthening the case of trading to ensure it goes on in a manner that would be desirable in the case of increasing the chances of better outcomes, about the different activities with which they are involved. Through such an action, the industry is also able to retain some level of sanity through ensuring that other sectors that depend on finance are not put at risk. The various amounts of money that investors could have brought in place could be used in the most desirable manner, in the case of ensuring that they do not predispose them to additional losses that would otherwise be handled for the general success of other industries. Artificial intelligence has also been of great benefit about standardization. As customer awareness becomes more enhanced in various parts of the world, the need for the

increase in the quality of products given out by different companies has also been of the essence. Through the particular case, companies have become obliged to ensure the various goods and products they put in place have the ability to attract and even retain many customers. One of the best methods that companies have had to rely on is the case of ensuring they have the potential to provide goods that are standardized. Through the process, they have a high possibility to retain the very element of success on having some level of consistency with the different products they put out on the market. Such an action is quite imperative as it increases the chances of the best outcomes of having products that meet the various quality dimensions put into place for the purpose of having benefits to customers.

Companies, therefore, make use of artificial intelligence to increase the level of standardization they carry out on their products for the case of improving the chances of having the best outcomes. Artificial intelligence has also been put into use in areas that would be of great harm to human life. The case, therefore, ensures that companies have the ability to protect the lives of different people who work for them through the process of substituting human subjects with artificial intelligence. One of the areas in which such a case is applied is in the mining industry. Some of the underground mines are usually quite dangerous for human subjects. In such a case, mining companies have been able to create vehicles and machines that can operate underground without being manned by people. In the event of any accidents such as the collapse of the walls of the mines, the different equipment used in the process of mining could be damaged, but the general lives of different people involved in the activities could be well-preserved. Some mining companies combine the use of both human and artificial intelligence for the purpose of attaining the kind of outcomes that would be desirable towards having the best outcomes as they relate to protecting the general lives of various individuals who regularly work in the mining industry. The use of such systems is also critical as it helps to assess the general situation found in the inner parts of the world. Through the given case, they can clearly identify some of the problems that could be associated with the inner parts of the ground for the purpose of increasing the chances for the best outcomes. The process also has a chance of showing some of the actions that the company could do to provide safe strategies for different employees who work in the mines, with a view to reducing the chances of harm.

RISKS AND MISCONCEPTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

In spite of the significant benefits associated with artificial intelligence, there is a chance that it could have far-reaching negative connotations upon various people who come into contact with it, either directly or indirectly. One of the uses that could be identified with the use of such technology is that it is only as good as the data put into it. Where the given data provides for a chance of having a misleading outcome, there is a high chance that it could bring about serious problems to that effect [10]. For instance, where a given hospital facility has installed a system that classifies Asthma as high-priority, it automatically declassifies pneumonia as high priority, unless the case is clearly stated too. In such a case, it creates significant problems where it fails to provide for the patients who are brought to it with the high level of urgency, they would need for the different health problems they have to be dealt with in the most efficient manner. A patient who happens to suffer from pneumonia could, therefore, be exposed to a high level of increased severity of the given problem that he may be suffering. Such a case would, therefore, increase the chances of an individual succumbing to the very health issue that could, otherwise, be well

handled. The patient, as a customer would lack the opportunity to benefit well from services offered at the health facility. Another risk of the use of artificial intelligence is that, by replacing human subjects, it brings in the general problem of putting people out of work. Companies which make use of artificial intelligence rely on reducing the number of human subjects with whom they are involved. The case, therefore, brings in some major problems given the fact that it reduces the number of people who have the chance of benefiting from the different employment opportunities that could be put across by such companies. Through such a process, there is a high chance that given companies could fail to create the very level of economic development that would be desirable in an area. The case would clearly show that such entities would lack the ability to provide a high level of employment that would be desirable. Employment would increase the overall amount of disposable income that people would be exposed to, for the sake of ensuring that they have the ability to meet some of their needs. Through the process, companies could lack the capacity to have a close engagement with their customers for the purpose of ensuring their needs are met. One of the misconceptions associated with the use of artificial intelligence as stated by Boutilier et al. is that it has a chance of creating the problem of replacing the very element of human intelligence. They state that it is an ethical case where more people seek to rely on artificial intelligence, they subscribe to the idea that human knowledge is not sufficient and, therefore, needs to be replaced with the use of machines and computers. Such a practice, therefore, sends the message that human beings do not have the capacity they require to handle various activities that would be determined to be of relevance to them. The process would also help human beings lose the general value towards humanity. The idea that people have been replaced in various quarters with the use of computers and machines is quite scary. It sends the general message that they are indispensable. Such a view is, however, quite misleading as people have the chance of keeping up with their general state and carry out various actions they are commonly involved with, towards attaining success. There is also the misconception that artificial intelligence has the chance of reducing the general level of emotions that people normally have. Where people are usually involved with the use of computer systems to solve problems that human beings used to handle, there is a chance that they could become out of touch with the general emotional aspect that the case could be having. The process would make them more geared towards looking at the success of the particular system they are working with, while at the same time giving a lesser chance for the creation of looking into the emotional aspects of the situation [9]. Such people become “converted into machines” for the process of ensuring they can meet some of the requirements put across to come up with the best practices as they relate to the different activities in which they are involved. Human beings can, however, not be converted into “machines.” They are, therefore, able to relate to customers in the most desirable manner for the process of ensuring they have the ability to meet their needs effectively.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence has its share of benefits and risks. The fact that it has a chance of creating the best outcomes for companies in ensuring they can develop high-quality products is quite important. Such companies have the ability to look into various ways through which they can deal with the different market needs that could exist. In such a case, there is a high chance that they would be in a good position to acquire a large number of customers for the various products they come up with. Artificial intelligence also ensures that companies have the ability to carry out the process of logistics. Through the given case, they would have the capacity to look into the

general rate of movement of the different goods they are involved with in a bid to ensure they can reach their destination in a timely fashion. The process would also contribute to ensuring that hospitals have to handle various patients correctly. On the flip side, artificial intelligence has the overall risk and misconceptions of replacing the very element of human beings as well as being less mindful of their emotional dimension, thereby, viewing them more of machines than human beings. Where used well, artificial intelligence can be used to transform customer engagement.

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